

A CORRELATIONAL STUDY BETWEEN CLOSE RELATIONSHIP ATTACHMENT STYLE AND SOCIAL ANXIETY

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A Correlational Study Between Close Relationship Attachment Style and Social Anxiety

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Abstract

The current study intends to investigate the correlation between attachment styles and social anxiety in undergraduate students, with a specific emphasis on college sophomores. The study used a descriptive correlational research method, with statistical analysis using the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient. Data were collected using two questionnaires: the Revised Adult Attachment Scale - Close Relationships Version, which examined people's attachment styles, and the Social Avoidance and Distress Scale (SADS), which assessed the degree of social anxiety across those who participated. The sample population included 101 second-year students from Far Eastern University - Manila (FEU) who were chosen using an intentional sampling method. The results of this investigation show a negative correlation between close and dependent attachment styles and social anxiety. Meanwhile, it has been determined that there is no substantial association between the anxiety attachment scale and social anxiety. This is because anxiety attachment patterns were found to have outliers. It has been found that 45.54% of participants exhibited fearful attachment styles, subsequently followed by preoccupied, secure, and dismissing attachment patterns. Furthermore, 94.06% of respondents had a high level of social anxiety, followed by ordinary social anxiety. Findings from the research help to provide college students with insight that will allow them to assess whether or not their current attachment styles in intimate relationships are beneficial in reducing their social anxiety. As proposed, this study could help educational institutions establish and promote conversations, discussion boards, and initiatives aimed at informing college students concerning the nuances of close relationships, promoting positive psychological health, and shepherding proactive and involvement efforts in higher education institutions.

Keywords: *social anxiety, attachment styles, undergraduate students*

Introduction

College represents a critical juncture of transitioning into adulthood, characterized by both intellectual and personal development. However, the experience is often fraught with stress, particularly as students navigate the challenges of separating from their traditional support networks, such as family and friends which can induce anxiety. Such experiences may be further exacerbated by new obstacles, such as managing heavy workloads, developing an independent identity, and living with roommates (LeBlanc & Marques, 2019). The existence of such college stressors is a probable predictor of psychological health diagnoses (Basch et al., 2020).

In the local context, data from Mendoza and Dizon (2022) indicate that 35.89% of the Filipino population have exhibited moderate to severe anxiety symptoms, especially amidst the pandemic. Approximately 45.7% of undergraduate students experience social anxiety (Cai et al., 2023), and 29.65% exhibit high levels of social anxiety (Obadeji & Kumolalo, 2022). These findings reinforce the issue that social anxiety is a typical problem among college students that warrants attention and assistance from institutions of higher education and healthcare professionals.

Social Anxiety is a psychological phenomenon characterized by fear in social situations. Fear in social situations generates difficulty with daily functioning that can last for six months (American Psychology Association, 2022). Individuals who are diagnosed with social anxiety disorders have substantial disabilities in social, work, and family areas, which harmfully impact their quality of life in comparison to individuals who came out negative in social anxiety (Hakami et al., 2017). Social anxiety can lead to concerns in confidence problems, adjustment issues, social isolation, academic performance, and interpersonal functioning (Kilcullen, n.d) These findings suggest that the impacts of social anxiety are detrimental to vulnerable college students affecting their later life.

Attachment styles are the distinctive way individuals interact with one another in close relationships, which is significantly impacted by one's worth and confidence (American Psychological Association, 2018). This study will primarily focus on the three attachment styles (a) anxiety, (b) depend, and (c) close attachment styles. Those who have anxious attachment styles are concerned about being disregarded or hated. Those individuals who have a dependent attachment style believe they can rely on others to be accessible in moments of need while close attachment style is a person's level of comfort with intimacy and closeness. A study conducted in 2020 discovered that a secure attachment has an excellent impact on college student achievement. Securely attached students had greater grade-point averages and finished at a greater rate compared to insecurely bonded students. Secured attachment showed a major impact on individuals' four-year cumulative GPA, with secure students achieving better GPAs than insecure students (Kurland & Siegel, 2020). Parpottas et al. (2023) study examines the implications of attachment qualities on college students' life satisfaction following the fourth phase of COVID-19 in Cyprus, with an emphasis on the intermediary function of psychological robustness. Their findings revealed substantial relationships across attachment qualities, mental resilience, and life happiness. Particularly, psychological robustness was discovered to significantly buffer the link involving attachment anxiety, attachment avoidance, as well as life happiness. Attachment anxiety and avoidance, in particular, had a detrimental impact on life fulfillment, which could be attributed to poorer instances of mental fortitude.

This study is anchored on the attachment theory of Kim Bartholomew (1990), which states that the primary tenet of attachment theory is that initial attachment ties with caregivers serve as a model for subsequent social interactions, and the purpose of the system of attachment is to maintain a sense of security. Bartholomew identified four attachment styles: (a) secure, (b) preoccupied, (c) dismissing, and (d) fearful. Secure attachment refers to loving and attentive parenting, which is anticipated to produce positive ideals of oneself and others, leading to secure and rewarding adult connections. The preoccupied attachment type is extremely reliant, defined by an unquenchable yearning for other people's acceptance and a sense of worthlessness. The dismissing attachment style is distinguished by a protective rejection of the need and urge for further social engagement. Finally, the fearful type of attachment is distinguished by a deliberate need for social interaction that is thwarted by concerns about its repercussions.

The researchers recognized this as a concern as it can greatly impact the decision-making, quality of life, and relationships of a vulnerable college student. In conducting a correlational study, the researchers investigated a potential link between attachment styles and social anxiety levels of sophomore undergraduate students. The study also aims to delve deeper into the nature of this relationship and explore possible underlying factors that may contribute to it. The findings of this study may contribute to finding healthy attachment styles, providing college students with knowledge, and allowing them to evaluate whether their present attachment styles in close relationships are effective in easing their social anxiety. Universities can potentially create and facilitate discussions, forums, and programs that focus on educating college students about the dynamics of close relationships, encouraging psychological well-being, and guiding preventative and intervention initiatives in college settings.

Research Questions

This study's primary purpose is to determine the correlation between attachment styles and social anxiety among sophomore undergraduate students. In particular, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of social anxiety among sophomore undergraduate students in relation to:
 - 1.1. low;
 - 1.2. average; and
 - 1.3. high?
2. What attachment style is common among sophomore undergraduate students?
3. What is the correlation between the attachment style and the social anxiety of sophomore undergraduate students, particularly in terms of:
 - 3.1 close and depend attachment style and social anxiety; and
 - 3.2 anxiety attachment style and social anxiety?

Literature Review

Understanding Social Support and Social Relationships

The emergence of novel obstacles and the consequent exploration for self-discovery, building social skills, and fostering personal growth leading to the development of social anxiety are inevitable. According to Hakulinen et al. (2016), social support is an external factor that is highly beneficial for an individual's mental health which can alleviate symptoms of anxiety, depression, and sleep disorders. Social support is composed of close interpersonal relationships, such as family, friends, and romantic relationships. A study has shown that social support cultivates a boost of confidence in their social ability and level, reducing the level of social anxiety (Jiang & Lou, 2021). Furthermore, self-esteem has been found to have a substantial association with anxiety, with individuals who possess high self-esteem being more resilient to anxiety and stress (Fernandes et al., 2021). Developing and sustaining strong social connections over an extended period brings about a shift in attachment bonds. Individuals' attachment style significantly influences their interpersonal relationships and has a lasting impact on their lives.

Attachment Style and Social Anxiety

Attachment style and social anxiety are strongly correlated to each other. A study by Clark et al. (2018) found a positive correlation between social anxiety and attachment anxiety as well as attachment avoidance. Attachment avoidance and anxiety were found to be positively associated with interpersonal apprehension such as social anxiety. They propose that both attachment aspects, attachment anxiety, and attachment avoidance, may be significant to comprehending social anxiety symptoms. This finding coincides with the exceedingly small amount of current research that has investigated social anxiety in connection to categorized indicators of attachment security and concluded that insecure attachment is related to greater intensity of symptoms in social anxiety. Furthermore, greater degrees of attachment anxiety and avoidance have been linked to elevated degrees of social anxiety indicators in a variety of relational settings.

There has been research that shows how attachment style can have an impact on college students in many ways such as stress, academic success, and life satisfaction. In the study by Dorin (2014) who explored the association involving university students' secure attachment and felt levels of stress, he discovered a strong correlation between adults' secure attachment and their perceived stress rates. College students with a secure attachment have reduced reported stress levels ($r = -.41, p < .001$) while adults who showed more insecure attachments expressed greater degrees of experienced distress.

Furthermore, a more recent study has discovered social anxiety is linked with insecure attachment styles, such as anxiety-related and avoidant attachments (Fattouh et al., 2022). Insecure attachment styles (preoccupied, fearful, and dismissing) were linked to increased dread, evasion, anxiety, and suicidal thoughts. A more preoccupied attachment style was linked with greater fear and avoidance. They discovered that insecure adolescents steer clear of getting acquainted with people as their sense of attachment did not meet their requirements as children, which helps to clarify why insecure attachment patterns were substantially connected with greater avoidance reviews. As a result, individuals became socially alienated, refusing to solicit support or consolation from others. They typically indicate an unhealthy relationship style. Furthermore, individuals with a style of attachment that is insecure exhibit poor self-image and judgment because they maintain emotional separation from others and refrain from personal interactions, which makes them susceptible to depression. This sort of attachment causes cognitive impairment, resulting in thoughts of suicide.

Irfan et al. (2023) discovered a substantial positive connection between anxious attachment style and social anxiety in college students. Anxious attachment type was found to foresee social anxiety by 19%. Furthermore, social anxiety and anxious attachment style showed a substantial distinction in gender, while avoidant attachment style did not. Manning et al. (2016) discovered that attachment style is connected with social anxiety. Cognitive factors and biological behaviors have been recognized as probable moderators.

Methodology

Research Design

The descriptive correlation method was employed in this study. The descriptive correlational method was utilized to explain the variables that affected one another. This study particularly examined and explained the correlation between attachment styles and social anxiety among second-year FEU-Manila students.

Participants

The research aimed to explore the function of different kinds of attachment in social anxiety among Far Eastern University-Manila second-year undergraduate students. A study on college university students in Germany found that social anxiety was rampant among freshmen and sophomores (Ahmad et al., 2017), therefore the study concentrated on second-year undergraduate students. Participants were gathered through a non-probability selection approach, notably purposive sampling. A total of 101 second-year undergraduate students were gathered to participate in this study. A minimum sample size of 100 increased the research's precision and quality. Furthermore, a high sample size decreased bias, identified outliers, and provided a more accurate depiction of the general population. To take part in the research investigation, participants had to meet the following eligibility specifications: (a) had to be a bonafide FEU Manila student, and (b) had to be in their second year of undergraduate studies regardless of program.

Instruments

The study employed two distinct instruments of inquiry for every variable to assess the types of attachment styles and social anxiety among FEU undergraduate students. The Social Avoidance and Distress Scale (SADS) and the Revised Adult Attachment Scale - Close Relationships Version.

The Social Avoidance and Distress Scale (SADS) was a questionnaire utilized to evaluate social anxiety, employing a true or false format to assess various aspects including anguish, discomfort, dread, and aversion. Social avoidance denoted the inclination to avoid interactions or engagement with others for various reasons. The assessment comprised 28 items, with respondents indicating whether each statement was true or false based on personal relevance. A score of 0 or 1 indicated low social anxiety, while scores ranging from 2 to 11 indicated average social anxiety, and scores of 12 or higher indicated high social anxiety. In 1969, Watson and Friend developed the psychometric properties of SADS through a survey of 205 undergraduates wherein they found out that SADS had high reliability, with an internal uniformity of 0.94 and test consistency of 0.68.

The Revised Adult Attachment Scale - Close Relationships Version was the assessment that was used to determine undergraduate students' style of attachment. The Adult Attachment Scale, RAAS - Close Relationship Version, had been developed by Collins and Read in 1990 to emphasize close relationships over romantic ones. It consisted of 18 items divided into three subscales: closeness, dependence, and anxiety. Research had shown strong reliability coefficients for the scale when used with undergraduate samples wherein Cronbach alphas for the close, depend, and anxiety subscales were .77, .78, and .85 accordingly. Respondents were asked to rate each question from 1 to 5 with 1 labeled as "Not at all characteristic of me" and 5 as "Very characteristic of me". Scoring was done by combining the ratings of the six items that made up each subscale, as specified, with items 1, 6, 8, 12, 13, and 17 falling under the Close subscale. The Depend subscale included numbers 2, 5, 7, 14, 16, and 18, while the Anxiety subscale included digits 3, 4, 9, 10, 11, and 15. In addition, items 8, 13, 17, 2, 7, 16, and 18 needed to be reverse scored prior to being included in the subscale mean.

Bartholomew's four attachment styles (secure, preoccupied, fearful, dismissing) have been acquired based on Collins' three attachment styles (close, depend, anxious). The researchers determined the average of close and depend attachment styles, which was then combined with the average of anxiety style following the method provided by the questionnaire. Below are the formulas used to establish and get the attachment styles of the participants. If the close and depend attachment style was > 3 and the anxiety attachment style was < 3 , the attachment style was secure. If the close and depend attachment style was > 3 and the anxiety attachment style was

> 3, the attachment style was preoccupied. If the close and depend attachment style was < 3 and the anxiety attachment style was < 3, the attachment style was dismissing. If the close and depend attachment style was < 3 and the anxiety attachment style was > 3, the attachment style was fearful.

Data Analysis

The data gathered through the survey has been assembled, processed, and analyzed for evaluation. The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was applied across the data evaluation since it allowed the researchers to determine whether or not it indicated a direct relationship involving two different variables, in this case, attachment style and social anxiety among FEU undergraduate students. The information obtained from the current research was analyzed using the IBM SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) application.

Procedure

The researchers examined the correlation between social anxiety and attachment styles among second-year undergraduate students at Far Eastern University in Manila. The study employed purposive sampling, and the participants were selected based on predetermined criteria relevant to the research objectives. In particular, Google Forms was used to collect data from the participants. Participants completed questionnaires that measured their social anxiety (using a Social Avoidance and Distress Scale) and attachment style (using a Revised Adult Attachment Scale - Close Relationships Version). Once the required data was gathered, the researchers utilized the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient statistical method to evaluate the correlation between the two variables. Finally, the researchers evaluated their results in context with the research questions and the existing pieces of literature. They examined the significance of the findings for understanding the link between social anxiety and attachment style. They further examined the study's weaknesses and potential areas for future investigation.

Ethical Considerations

Informed Consent. The researchers ensured that participants have been provided with comprehensive information and a clear understanding of the data they would be contributing, along with the potential risks and benefits associated with their participation in the study.

Voluntary Participations. Participants had the right to voluntarily take part in the research, and they were entitled to request the deletion of some, or all, of the records associated with their involvement. This ensured that participants were in control of their participation and could choose to withdraw at any time.

Anonymity. The data was anonymized by the researchers to ensure that the participants remained unidentifiable, thus preventing any possibility of linking the data back to individual participants.

Confidentiality. All information collected during the process was handled with the utmost confidentiality. We ensured that the participation of all involved parties was kept private and not disclosed to any unauthorized individuals.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings according to the study's research questions. Results were obtained from the collected data.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics and Pearson's R Correlation for Study Variables

Variable	M	SD	1	2	3
1. Close and Depend Subscale	2.8673	2.8673	-	-	-
2. Anxiety Subscale	3.4941	1.00078	-.444**	-	-
3. Social Anxiety	15.7327	2.87712	-.248*	.193	1

n = 101 **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

This study's primary purpose is to examine the correlation between attachment types and social anxiety among second-year undergraduate students at FEU-Manila. The goal of this study is to look into determining a potential link between attachment types and social anxiety in undergraduate students. As a result, this study employed a descriptive-correlation analysis approach to analyze the respondents' styles of attachment and social anxiety.

The results from attachment style have shown the majority of the participants exhibit fearful attachment styles which represents 45.54% of the total sample. Preoccupied attachment styles, on the other hand, make up 22.77% of the respondents. Those with secure attachment styles comprise 15.84% of the sample, while 8.91% of the participants display dismissing attachment styles. It is also worth noting that outliers were also present, in which 7 out of 101 participants did not produce any attachment style.

The results from the data on social anxiety reveal that the vast majority of student respondents, specifically 94.06%, exhibit a high degree of social anxiety while 5.94% report experiencing average social anxiety. None of them garner low social anxiety.

Table 1 shows the correlation between attachment styles and social anxiety. Close and depend attachment style is negatively correlated with social anxiety by ($r = -.248, p < .05$). This finding suggests that an increased presence of the close and dependent attachment style

is linked to a reduction in social anxiety.

The close attachment style, similar to the secure attachment style, is characterized by a balanced and adaptable method of connecting with people in relationships that are distinguished by emotions of safety, confidence, and satisfaction in close interactions (Robinson et al., 2024). According to Wang (2023), they are typically characterized by a positive self-image and a positive perception of others. Research has shown that they are more likely to utilize effective approaches to regulate their emotions, leading to better mental and emotional well-being. Furthermore, they are considerably comfortable seeking support from others on periods they require assistance and demonstrate a greater ability to effectively manage negative emotions. People with a secure attachment style show less socially anxious characteristics. It is believed to stem from loving and attentive parenting in infancy, establishing the framework for secure and rewarding adult relationships throughout maturity (Bartholomew, 1990). However, individuals exhibiting secure attachment styles still experience social anxiety to a lesser degree than those with an insecure attachment style (Guo & Ash, 2020). It is crucial to realize that social anxiety can exist even in those with a stable attachment style. A variety of factors may influence an individual's social anxiety. Environmental pressures, genetic make-up, and even past traumatic occurrences are all factors to consider.

A further finding is that anxiety/anxious attachment style does not correlate significantly with social anxiety ($r = .193$, $p > 0.05$), implying that changes in anxious attachment style do not correspond with variations in social anxiety. The current investigation discovered outliers in the data findings in the attachment styles. These outliers may have decreased the value of the correlation coefficient, causing the anxiety attachment type to not correlate with social anxiety.

This result is similar to the findings of McCarty (2005), who discovered that a socially anxious cohort exhibited a mostly insecure attachment type, particularly fearful and anxious categories. They discovered that people with an insecure attachment style were not significantly more socially nervous. Most of the studies found that anxious attachment style is correlated with social anxiety. In a study by Eng et al. (2001), they found that individuals in the anxious attachment group had higher levels of social anxiety and aversion, despair, disability, and less life fulfillment than those who were part of the secure attachment group.

Differences can occur for an array of factors, all of which may have been attributed to the variables' lack of association. One example is the intricacy of social anxiety, which is a multilayered concept that involves a variety of elements including biological factors such as brain activity and chemicals, heredity, disposition, prior interactions, and mental constructs (Mathew et al., 2001). The second factor could be the variety of attachment styles. It is vital to highlight that the anxious attachment style is only one among several. Attachment styles are not binary, but rather emerge on a spectrum, with people experiencing varied levels of attachment-related anxiousness. Finally, there are mediating elements to consider, including interpersonal assistance and dysfunctional methods of coping.

Conclusion

College is a battleground that shapes and prepares individuals for their futures. As a result, they may experience anxiety due to a variety of circumstances. Anxiety, particularly social anxiety, can have a bearing on a person's college life, affecting anything from making choices to relationships with others. The major goal of this study is to evaluate the correlation between attachment style and social anxiety in sophomore college students. The study found that there is a correlation between attachment style and social anxiety particularly in close and depend attachment styles. This indicates that the attachment style, close and depend impacts their social anxiety negatively, causing it to increase or decrease in opposite directions. A variety of attachment styles affect social anxiety. The study has found that there is no significant relationship between anxiety attachment style and social anxiety which may impact their social life and social relationship in a positive and negative manner.

The most common adult attachment style displayed by second-year undergraduate students is fearful attachment style, subsequently followed by preoccupied, secure, and dismissive attachment styles. Additionally, the vast majority of respondents have severe social anxiety, followed by average social anxiety in the higher-education setting. As a result, it is possible to conclude that a vast majority of students have a fearful adult attachment style, which contributes to their high social anxiety.

Attachment styles and social anxiety have an effect on each other to some extent, and while there have been few studies on the correlation between these variables, the researchers hope that this study will aid in even further comprehending the correlation between attachment style and social anxiety, allowing it to assist students in their college journey. Furthermore, the study's observations may assist university administration in developing conversations, and initiatives aimed at cultivating undergraduates regarding the complexities of close relationships, promoting psychological wellness, and steering assistance programs in educational institutions. Developing a program to assist sophomores and other college students enduring social anxiety could aid them build healthy attachment patterns and reduce their indications of social anxiety, resulting in a positive social relationship with other people.

Due to constraints such as a relatively small sample of respondents, it is recommended that the findings of the present research be cautiously interpreted. Taking this into account, further investigation is needed to clarify and build an even more comprehensive and impartial inquiry into the issue.

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